

TRENDS AND INSIGHTS INTO GLYMPHATIC SYSTEM RESEARCH AND ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS FROM 2014 TO 2023

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Background: Over the past decade, research on the Glymphatic System (GS) has gained increasing attention within the scientific community. This system, initially explored through animal models and MRI tracer-based studies, holds potential implications for understanding neurodegenerative diseases (ND), notably Alzheimer's Disease (AD). However, there is a lack of comprehensive bibliometric analysis integrating GS research with investigations into AD pathology. *Objective:* To conduct a bibliometric analysis to synthesize the evolving landscape of GS research, particularly focusing on its intersection with AD pathology. *Methods:* We utilized the Web of Science Core Collection (WoSCC) database to retrieve and analyze relevant literature published between 2014 and 2023. The search strategy encompassed a broad set of Mesh terms related to GS and AD, focusing on original research articles, reviews, and early access publications. Statistical techniques, including citation analysis, co-authorship networks, and thematic clustering of author keywords, were employed to provide a comprehensive overview. *Results:* Our analysis covered 1,681 documents sourced from 618 unique publications, involving contributions from 10,940 authors worldwide. The study revealed a steady increase in publication output over the decade, with notable international collaboration observed in 30.81% of documents. On average, each document received approximately 29.84 citations, underscoring the impact of research output. Significant contributions came from leading institutions such as Columbia University, Washington University, and Zhejiang University, with the United States and China emerging as key contributors in scientific production and citation impact. *Discussion:* The findings highlight the critical role of the GS in ND, particularly AD, while also revealing disparities in research capacity and collaboration globally. Methodological considerations include variations in imaging protocols and the impact of citation practices on perceived research impact. The analysis underscores the need for enhanced interdisciplinary collaboration and methodological standardization to advance understanding and therapeutic interventions for AD. *Conclusion:* This bibliometric analysis provides a comprehensive synthesis of GS research and its implications for AD. Addressing disparities in research capacity and fostering global collaboration are crucial steps toward developing effective therapeutic strategies and enhancing knowledge of ND.

Keywords: Neuroscience; Alzheimer's Disease; Bibliometric Analysis; WoSCC; Demetia